

Synthesis of 2-(2-Arylviny)thiopyrano- [2,3-*d*]pyrimidines

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PREVIOUSLY, we reported the synthesis of thieno-[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines via the reaction of variously substituted 5-acetyl-4-mercaptopyrimidines with activated halomoethylene compounds¹. Further studies have shown that the reaction of diethyl maleate with 5-acetyl-4-mercaptopyrimidines (**1a-c**) takes a different course forming diethyl 2-(2-arylviny)-4,5-dimethylthiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-6,7-dicarboxylate (**2a-c**) instead of the isomeric thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (**3**). The structural assignment of **2** is substantiated by its ir and pmr spectra. The ir spectrum shows two CO bands at 1 710 and 1 640 cm^{-1} corresponding to unconjugated and conjugated esters, respectively and the pmr spectrum shows a methinyl proton as a singlet at δ 4.9. These spectral data clearly establish the thiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine as the correct structure for the product².

The conversion of compounds **1a-c** to the corresponding thiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (**2a-c**) presumably takes place as illustrated in Scheme 1. This involves first formation of the open form-A, the latter then undergoes intramolecular condensation to give **2a-c**. When 5-acetyl-4-mercaptopyrimidines (**1a-c**) were allowed to react with one equivalent of maleic anhydride in refluxing bromobenzene the product which formed directly was thiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (**4a-c**). The postulated intermediate (B) was not isolated under the conditions of the reaction but cyclised to **4** (Scheme 1).

The synthetic method was extended to the preparation of thiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines. Thus the cycloaddition reaction of **1a-c** with *N*-phenylmaleimide afforded thiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines of type 5. Interestingly, the reaction of compounds **1a-c** with cinnamic acid derivatives under the same conditions yielded the corresponding 4-(β -carboxyethylmercapto)pyrimidine derivatives (**6a-c**) respectively, and none of the possible *N*- β -carboethoxyethyl derivatives (**7** or **8**) were formed. The structures of compounds **6a-c** were established by the fact that they reacted with hydrazine hydrate to give pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine (**9**), also its uv spectra being closely similar to the β -cyanoethylpyrimidine (**10**). Studies dealing with the cyclisation of these pyrimidines (**6**) are now in progress.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Microanalyses were carried out at the Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded

on a Varian HA 100 instrument (100 MHz) in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference. The starting 5-acetyl-4-mercaptopyrimidines (**1a-c**) were obtained following the literature procedure³.

Diethyl-2-(2-arylviny)-4,5-dimethylthiopyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-6,7-dicarboxylate (2a-c**):** A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and diethyl maleate (0.01 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The solid product that separated after cooling was collected and crystallised as pale yellow crystals (50–55%) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA
OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	250–61	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₈ S
2b	240–42	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₈ S
2c	163–65	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₈ S
4a	260–61	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
4b	235–36	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
4c	173–74	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
5a	208–05	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
5b	212–13	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
5c	182–88	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S
6a	239–40	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ SO ₄ Cl ₂
6b	174–75	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ SO ₄ Cl
6c	165–66	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ SO ₄

^ν_{max} **2b** 990 (CH=CH *trans*), 1 640 (CO, conjugated), 1 715 (CO unconjugated); **4b** 990 (OH=CH *trans*), 1 640 (CO, conjugated), 1 720 (CO unconjugated); **4c** 980 (CH=CH *trans*), 1 650 (CO), 1 705 (CO); **5a** 990 (CH=CH *trans*), 1 645 (CO, conjugated), 1 715 (CO, unconjugated); **5b** 985 (CH=CH *trans*), 1 650 (CO), 1 715 (CO); **6a** 985 (CH=CH *trans*), 1 665 (CO), 1 670 (CO), 3 100–3 350br (OH); **6b** 985 (OH=CH *trans*), 1 660 (CO), 1 670 (CO), 3 115–3 350br cm^{-1} (OH); δ (DMSO) **2c** 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 1.29 (t, 3H, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.7 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.9 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 3.8 (1H, s, methinyl proton), 6.3–6.6 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, OH=CH), 6.6–6.9 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, OH=CH), 7.3–7.7 (5H, m, ArH); **4a** 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (1H, s, methinyl proton), 6.0–6.3 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz, CH=CH), 6.6–6.9 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz, CH=CH), 7.3–7.7 (5H, m, ArH); **5a** 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.75 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (1H, s, methinyl proton), 6.0–6.3 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz, CH=CH), 6.6–6.9 (1H, d, *J* 17 Hz, CH=CH), 7.5–8.0 (10H, m, ArH); λ_{max} (ϵ_{max}) **1b** 370 (4 539), **6a** 314 (29.300), 230 (8.529); **10** 390 (28.200), 240 nm (7.843).

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Reaction of 1a-c with maleic anhydride: A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and maleic anhydride (0.01 mol) in bromobenzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid product that obtained after cooling was collected and crystallised from benzene as colourless crystals (60–70%) (Table 1).

Reaction of 1a-c with N-phenylmaleimide: Following the above experimental conditions and using *N*-phenylmaleimide instead of maleic anhydride, precipitated compounds **5a-c** were crystallised from benzene as pale yellow crystals (50–55%) (Table 1).

2-(2-Arylviny)-4-(1-aryl-2-carboxyethylmercapto)-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidines (6a-c**):** A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and cinnamic acid derivatives (0.01

NOTES

Scheme 1

mol) in bromobenzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid obtained after cooling was crystallised from methanol as pale yellow crystals (60–70%) (Table 1).

Action of hydrazine on compound 6: A mixture of 6a (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After cooling, the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals. The m.p. of the

compound was compared with an authentic sample of compound 9 and was found to be identical.

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Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of a Few Heterocycles derived from 6-Chloro-5H-2,3-dihydro-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thione

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In continuation of our earlier studies¹ on the orientation of cyclisation in the reaction of unsymmetrical mercaptoazoles with bifunctional compounds, we report herein the results of our study on the reaction of unsymmetrical azine (mercaptoindolotriazine) with alkylhalides and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline.

Condensation of 6-chloro-5H-2,3-dihydro-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thione (2), obtained by the

reaction of 7-chloroisatin with thiosemicarbazide followed by the cyclisation of the intermediate 7-chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1) with alkali, with 1,2-dibromoethane was likely to give 9-chloro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (3) or 6-chloro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2',3':3,4]-[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (6) or both depending on the mode of cyclisation. However, the reaction of 2 with 1,2-dibromoethane gave a single product (tlc) to which the structure 3 and not 6 was assigned, as the product was not identical with an authentic sample of 6 obtained by the reaction of 1 with 1,2-dibromoethane (Scheme 1).

The amide carbonyl ($-NH-C=O$) absorption 1695 cm^{-1} in 1, was found absent in the ir spectrum of the product obtained by the reaction of 1 with 1,2-dibromoethane. This corroborated the cyclic structure of 6. The structures 3 and 6 were further supported by their pmr spectral data.

Similarly, the condensation of 2 with 1,3-dibromopropane and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline yielded 10-chloro-4H-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (4) and 11-chloroquinoxalino[2',3':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]indolo[2,3-*e*][1,2,4]triazine (5) respectively as they were not found to be identical with their authentic angular isomers 7 and 8 obtained from 1 by similar treatment with 1,3-dibromopropane and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline respectively.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) KOH, (ii) BrCH₂CH₂Br, (iii) BrCH₂CH₂CH₂Br, (iv) 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline, NaOAc.